

The National Association for Gifted Children

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Charity No. S10217Z Company limited by guarantee: registered in England No. 905037 Director Henry Collis, T.D., M.A.

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HC:ce

Dear Professor Jaffar,

I am very glad to welcome you as a member of this Association and hope that you will find our work of interest. I know that we shall considerably benefit by keeping in touch with you in view of the study you have made concerning gifted children, particularly on creativity and brain mechanisms.

We very much hope that you can attend the World Conference to be held in London this September. It is the first of its kind to take place and as you will see from the enclosed brochure it is being run with the cooperation of our government. We hope that it will lead to a series of such Conferences in different countries and it would therefore seem of great importance that somebody with your interest in gifted children should be in on these Conferences from the beginning.

We have been fortunate in securing some of the leading experts in understanding the needs of gifted children.

Yours sincerely,

CREATIVITY AND BRAIN MECHANISMS

Dr Nouri Jaffar, Baghdad University, Iraq

My intensive study since 1960 on creativity and brain mechanisms, which is to be published next year, and which is based on Soviet neuropsychology, reveals that creativity or giftedness is a complex cortical functional system having as its contents a social-historical foundation and exhibiting in its brain structure different levels of organisation. The creative process takes place as a result of combined activity of several cortical zones of hierarchical order, each plays its own specific role and supplies a cortical link for the normal functioning of the brain as a whole. Soviet neuropsychologists follow the historical approach in studying human psychological processes to discover their organic basis and social origin. They show that the mental life of higher animals, however complex, is the outcome of two main factors: innate tendencies and direct, individual experience formed in the course of life which is not communicable and disappears with the death of the particular animal.

For more information on the lecture please contact: nouri.jaffar@gmail.com

Please contact World Council for Gifted and Talented Children at
<http://www.world-gifted.org>